

Data-driven analysis for the characterization of household appliance ownership and use in Sub-Saharan Africa

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ABSTRACT

To grant reliable and affordable electricity provision to non-electrified communities, proper system sizing, based on accurate demand estimation is crucial. However, the absence of historical data, and scarce, scattered, and often unreliable pre-electrification surveys, make this process particularly prone to errors. Acquiring data, especially with high quality and detail, is difficult, time-consuming and expensive. Even though, in a few site-specific cases the limited data collected has allowed researchers to develop methodologies to generate synthetic demand profiles based on variegated site-specific socio-economic information and appliance adoption patterns. However, given the lack of comprehensive datasets of such information, the use of synthetic methodologies has been circumscribed to limited regional and socio-economic scopes. This research proposes the development of a data-driven machine-learning framework for estimating appliance adoption patterns with a subset of relevant socio-economic indicators, identified throughout a comprehensive literature analysis and data collection across various sources. To successfully train the model, a novel open-access database has been created and populated with socio-economic information combined with appliance data collected from public and private sources. Finally, a structured logistic regression analysis has been performed, not only to capture the nexus of socio-economic factors with appliance adoption but also to estimate the most relevant ones. The methodology calibrated with the proposed open-access database has shown 71.7 % accuracy, which represents an important achievement in the field. The study's findings lay the foundations for simplifying the estimation of appliance adoption, which can facilitate the demand estimation for sizing rural energy systems and rural electrification approaches.

Table of Abbreviations

CEFA	Comitato Europeo per la Formazione Agraria
CLASP	Collaborative Labelling and Appliance Standards Program
CV	cross validation
DC	developing country
D _{ed} C	developed country
ESMAP	Energy Sector Management Assistance Program
FN	false negative
FP	false positive
FUNAE	Fundo de Energia
HH	household
HHH	household's head
LSMS+	Living Standards Measurement Study – Plus
NaN	not a number

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CEFA	Comitato Europeo per la Formazione Agraria
PV	photovoltaic
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SHS	solar home system
SME	small medium enterprise
SSA	Sub Saharan Africa
TN	true tegative
TP	true positive

1. Introduction

Energy plays a crucial role in addressing modern global challenges,

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as emphasized by the 7th Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) of the United Nations in the Agenda2030. It enables local development [1,2] by facilitating the creation of income-generating activities, which can reinforce growth through a positive feedback loop. However, energy is not the sole determinant; socio-economic, infrastructural and cultural factors also exert a strong influence [3–5]. Despite its priority, achieving universal access by 2030 under SDG7 remains out of reach [6], a situation exacerbated by Covid-19 pandemic, which slowed the process [7].

Access to electricity is lower in rural areas than in urban ones [8]. The centralized demand of urban areas justifies the investment in expensive infrastructure, such as national grid extension. Conversely, scattered and scarcely populated areas, such as the rural ones in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) [9], are often better served by decentralized energy sources, which require lower initial investments and can be tailored to local needs. Data challenges also pose a barrier, as information is often scattered across multiple sources, inconsistent in format, and limited in quantity or quality [10]. This hinders the profitability of projects and the deployment of solutions to improve the conditions of the average SSA household, which today consumes less than 20 % of the energy consumed by households in Developed Countries (DedCs) [11].

The financial viability of decentralized energy projects depends on accurate planning to meet community needs, or demand. Oversized designs hinder cost recovery [12], and increase tariffs and upfront costs [13,14]. Undersized systems may slow down local development by failing to meet demand growth [15] or by providing unreliable supply, limiting growth [16].

Demand assessment has traditionally relied on pre-electrification interviews, which are often inaccurate [17,18]. Alternative modern approaches use computer models, for planning [19] and load prediction [20]. Bottom-up models offer high accuracy in demand estimation [21, 22] and long-term trends identification [23], through data-driven approaches that capture local dynamics. However, their scalability remains uncertain, due to limited data for calibration and validation,

including appliance adoption information [19]. Efforts to address data issues through regrouping and harmonization have shown limited success [17]. Data availability remains a significant challenge, as it is often fragmented, inconsistent, or of poor quality [10].

This data scarcity is a significant barrier to deployment of energy access projects that this study seeks to address.

This study proposes a data-driven machine-learning framework to estimate appliance adoption based on socio-economic and geographical factors across Sub-Saharan countries. A comprehensive literature review identifies key determinants of energy demand, while a data harmonization process creates a novel open database to train the model. Major socio-economic and geographical factors are identified through the review, and relevant data sources are collected and harmonized. Logistic regression models are then developed to estimate appliance adoption, highlighting the most relevant input factors for prediction.

This study introduces several novelties: the development of data-driven machine-learning models to estimate appliance adoption with a regional scale for electrification planning, the creation and harmonization of a database of socio-economic and geographical indicators appliance adoption estimation, the identification of key input factors to improve prediction accuracy and enable simplified models, and the calibration and validation of the proposed comprehensive procedure.

Fig. 1 provides an overview of the work, detailing the three steps leading to the final goal: constructing a prediction algorithm trained on a database of appliance adoption patterns and socio-economic conditions, with explicit references to the sections.

2. Literature review on rural communities load demand estimation

A review of the scientific literature is conducted to identify the main drivers influencing community electricity demand, forming the foundation for constructing the appliance ownership database. To accelerate

Fig. 1. Structure of the three steps that compose the activity of the work.

the development of energy projects, priority was given to studies that provide inputs for Energy Planning Models.

The review focused on energy access research within the last 15 years, with a focus on drivers impacting electricity consumption. A systematic search was performed using Scopus with keywords: ("electricity demand" OR "load profile" OR "appliance ownership" OR "demand evolution" OR "electricity consumption patterns" OR "determinants" OR "driver"). Relevant studies were identified through a manual examination of the selected works that mentioned energy demand determinants, which findings are discussed in this section.

The review has two objectives: to identify drivers previously used to explain variations in load profiles, energy consumption, and appliance adoption, and to establish a starting point for this study, by summarizing state of the art of the methodologies for rural areas demand estimation, which this work aims to refine and build upon.

A total of 39 works, including five reviews, were identified and analysed. While the focus was on studies regarding DCs, selected applications to D_{ed}Cs were included when their methodology were relevant and applicable to DCs.

As pointed out by Debnath and Mourshed [24], the majority of current Energy Planning Models were created in D_{ed}Cs and often rely on assumptions that fail to address the unique challenges of DCs. These

challenges include meeting basic socio-economic needs and estimating suppressed demand, which are taken for granted in D_{ed}Cs but requires tailored solutions in DCs. Similarly, demand estimation for un-electrified areas must account for households that may have no prior experienced with electricity, necessitating customized approaches.

Research efforts have been carried out to fill the gap. In their review of energy planning case studies in remote areas of DCs, Riva et al. [19] proposed a classification in terms of spatial coverage, planning horizon, energy carrier, decision criteria, mathematical model, and demand sector. They found that spatial coverage influenced the selected approach. Large-scale planning at regional or national levels often relied on simplistic, top-down methods using aggregated data to estimate demand and its evolution over time. In contrast, small-scale systems planning employed more complex, bottom up, models that utilized on-field data, better capturing local socio-economic and cultural dynamics. Data scarcity, however, often limited these models, forcing them to adopt simplified assumption, such as fixed demand over time.

Kuster et al. [20] reviewed 113 electrical load forecasting models, emphasizing the intensive data requirements of bottom-up approaches for long-term demand prediction. Their study classified model input variables into socio-economic, environmental (e.g.: weather conditions), building and occupancy (e.g.: dwelling characteristics), and

Table 1
Classes of drivers identified in literature.

Publication	Socio-economic	Dwelling	Appliance	Past demand	Supply	Alternative energy sources	Geographical	Cultural
Literature with focus on Appliance Adoption								
[29]					X			
[26]	X	X	X		X			X
[27]	X	X	X			X	X	X
[28]	X		X				X	X
Literature with focus on Aggregated Electricity Demand								
[31]	X	X				X		
[32]	X				X			
[17]	X							
[33]	X				X	X		
Literature with focus on Load Profile								
[39]				X				
[22]	X		X					
[42]				X	X			
[18]			X					
[21]	X		X					
[43]	X			X	X		X	
[37]	X	X	X				X	X
[40]	X	X	X	X	X			
[41]	X		X					X
[38]				X			X	
[36]	X	X	X	X			X	
[35]	X	X	X	X	X			
Literature with focus on Demand Evolution								
[44]	X				X			
[1]	X		X	X	X	X	X	X
[45]	X		X	X	X	X	X	X
[47]	X		X	X	X	X	X	X
Literature with Multiple Foci								
[48]	X	X				X	X	
[49]	X	X					X	
[51]	X	X	X		X	X		
[55]	X			X				
[56]	X				X			
[50]	X	X	X					
[53]	X							
[54]	X	X	X	X		X	X	
[52]	X	X	X			X		
[57]	X			X				X
Total	29	12	17	13	14	10	11	9

time-index (e.g.: past demand data).

Jones et al. [25] categorized determinants of electric consumption into socio-economic, dwelling and appliance factors. This classification has been adopted and expanded in this work to include additional drivers identified in the literature review.

The final classification of drivers encompasses socio-economic, dwelling, appliance, past-demand, supply, alternative energy sources, geographical and cultural factors. Socio-economic drivers broadly cover social and economic conditions at both community and individual levels, such as population density, household income and composition, and business revenues. Dwelling drivers relate to household characteristics like the number of rooms, while appliance drivers focus on factors such as price and nominal power. Past-demand data includes modelling techniques relying on historical electricity usage, such as past load profiles. Supply drivers address the supply side of the electric system, including the number of hours of electricity availability. Drivers related to alternative energy sources consider factors such as the price of kerosene or candles. Geographical drivers account for location-specific characteristics, such as climate zones and distance from the nearest city. Cultural drivers involve societal habits and practices.

The analysed publications are categorized by their focus - appliance ownership, aggregated electricity demand, load profile, demand evolution over time, and multiple foci. Each study is briefly presented to derive insights into the methodologies and drivers relevant to this work. [Table 1](#) summarizes the factor classes and their corresponding drivers as identified in the literature.

2.1. Focus - appliance ownership

Regression techniques were employed in all studies modelling appliance ownership. Rao and Ummel [26] employed logistic regression and boosted regression trees to predict ownership of refrigerators, washing machines and television. two covariates sets were assessed: a sparse set (income and urbanization) and a diverse set (socio-economic and cultural factors). The results showed that the input variable set had a greater impact on prediction accuracy than the choice of the model. Kurata et al. [27] used ordinary least squares regression on field survey data in Bangladesh to predict solar home systems (SHS) ownership, differentiating residential and business users. They found business users more sensitive to energy costs. Similarly, Richmond et al. [28] applied ordinary least square models to data from 5000 Indian households, analysing the influence of electrification duration on appliance ownership. Ownership was evaluated by single appliances, ownership tiers, and the number of appliances per type. Time since electrification positively influenced all outcomes, emphasizing the need to account for time dynamics in system sizing.

A survey in Western Kenya [29] examined the relationship between household connection type (national grid, SHS, or no connection) and appliance ownership. SHSs influenced ownership of phone chargers and televisions, but had limited impact on other appliances. SHS users were generally of higher socioeconomic statuses compared to households relying on kerosene or without electricity. As Lukuyu [30] noted, SHS represent a key step in the energy ladder, improving electricity access, and enabling higher appliance ownership through economic development.

2.2. Focus - aggregated electricity demand

Louw et al. [31] estimated average electricity demand of two rural villages in South Africa by collating two survey-based datasets. Using a log-linear regression model, tested the significance of various input variables and identified income as a key driver, concluding that the use of electricity is cost-sensitive. Azadeh et al. [32] used regression alongside an artificial neural network to estimate annual household electricity consumption in Iran. Dominguez et al. [33] applied linear regression to analyse electricity demand and its main drivers in rural

Kenya. Blodgett et al. [17] compared metered demand data with survey-based bottom-up estimates for eight Kenyan communities. Their findings revealed that survey-based methods overestimated demand by 330 %, potentially leading to substantial sizing error. The authors proposed a proxy methodology, supported by an analysis of variance (ANOVA) test, which demonstrated that consumers from different communities belonged to the same sample population. This approach allowed consumption data to be interchanged, reducing estimation errors without requiring distance metrics, thereby simplifying the analysis and focusing on available data.

2.3. Focus - load profile

Hartvigsson and Ahlgren [18] conducted a survey-based demand estimation in a Tanzanian village to assess its accuracy in predicting load profiles. Despite the village having electricity for over 10 years, survey responses underestimated actual metered usage. While traditional bottom-up, survey-based approaches often lead to poor system sizing, innovative methods in the literature show promising results. LoadProGen [22] and RAMP [21] are stochastic load profile generators that use the same data pool of traditional approaches, such as planned appliances and usage patterns. However, Takalani et al. [34] highlighted the unreliability of surveyed data on planned appliances purchases, underscoring the need for methodologies that estimate appliance adoption using socio-economic and weather data. RAMP has also been integrated into the M-LED platform [35], a demand estimation tool that combines multi-sectorial, granular data to generate monthly load curves for rural communities.

Adeoye and Spataru [36] simulated and forecasted hourly and yearly power consumption for 14 West African countries for 2016 and 2030 using a hybrid demand model combining top-down and bottom-up approaches. The model accounted for nine household appliances types, occupancy patterns, weather, day type, and daylight hours to estimate hourly electricity usage in urban and rural electrified households. By incorporating a random generator, national survey occupancy data, and average appliance operation timings, the model calculated the synthetic likelihood of appliance usage.

Caquilpan et al. [37] developed a novel method to estimate home load profiles by combining electrical power consumption and socio-demographic data. Self-organizing maps, a neural network, classified homes based on unique characteristics, while a probabilistic model using Bayesian networks simulated appliance behaviour, incorporating daily demand variations.

Few et al. [38], applied an open-source framework for microgrid design to estimate load demand, optimize cost, and characterize systems. Their study evaluated the influence of weather, rurality and non-domestic demand on microgrid demand profiles. They found that weather impacts, particularly in hot regions, increase with higher levels of energy access, with cooling technologies such as fan and refrigerators affecting nighttime demand.

Hernandez et al. [39] demonstrated the application of machine learning for short-term microgrid load forecasting, using only two years of past consumption data and a consumption calendar.

Similarly Dominguez et al. [40] used supervised and unsupervised models to estimate hourly lighting load profiles in rural Kenyan and Tanzanian households. Their models integrated publicly available data at multiple scales with satellite imagery.

Scott and Coley [41] analysed metered data from two Tanzanian solar PV diesel hybrid mini-grids, categorizing homes are based on demand attributes. By integrating load profile data with household demographics and appliance ownership, they concluded that socioeconomic status, occupancy, and appliance ownership shape load profiles.

Using data from eleven East African microgrids over two years, Williams et al. [42] examined weekly and monthly seasonality in consumption and long-term growth patterns. While most systems showed

demand growth, no universal trend emerged. Additionally, customers exhibited a preference for frequent, small payments, when given flexible tariff options, highlighting the importance of considering payment frequency in tariff models.

Lorenzoni et al. [43] developed a database of load profiles from sixty-one mini-grid projects in DCs. A clustering identified archetypal profiles, followed by graphical analysis to explore factors influencing load profile shapes.

2.4. Focus - demand evolution

Fobi et al. [44] conducted a longitudinal study of Kenyan residential electricity consumption, to explore demand evolution over time, addressing a gap identified in Ref. [19]. Their findings showed an overall increase in consumption, with urban households experiencing higher growth than rural ones. This underscores the importance of including urban-rural distinctions in future studies.

Riva et al. [45,46] developed and calibrated a System Dynamics model to examine the relationship between socio-economic variables and electricity demand in a Tanzanian rural community. The model, based on causal-loop diagrams from earlier work [1], captures a positive feedback loop between electricity provision and community socio-economic characteristics. It was further tested in a subsequent study [47].

2.5. Multiple foci

Most reviewed works cover multiple focuses. Van Ruijven et al. [48] critiqued global energy models for excessive aggregation, building a bottom-up model to estimate household energy use, including cooking, water heating, space heating needs, appliance ownership, and lighting. Inputs included household (e.g., expenditure) and community (e.g., population) variables. Daioglou et al. [49] extended this model to five DCs, whereas the original analysis focused on India. Riva et al. [50] further built on Van Ruijven’s model combining load estimation, load profile generation and system sizing for an Indian rural community.

Fabini et al. [51], used k-nearest neighbours’ regression to predict the increase in appliance ownership expected after electrification. Socio-economic metrics, were employed to assess proximity between

Kenyan wards, with ownership in electrified wards serving as a basis for predictions in unelectrified ones. These ownerships estimates were then converted into electricity demand using typical appliance consumption values. As Fabini et al. state: “Implicit in this approach is the assumption that localities that share socioeconomic characteristics will also have similar demand for electricity services and similar ability to pay for them.” This methodology aligns with the proxy approach from Ref. [17], while introducing multidimensional distance metrics. However, the limited focus on socio-economic features could reduce predictive accuracy, suggesting that expanding the range of input features could enhance results.

Allee et al. [52] also employed machine learning models, emphasizing the value of on-field data for proxy based approaches, despite the poor reliability of survey based appliance ownership data. They performed variable importance tests to reduce data collection needs, offering potential time and cost savings. In contrast, Shibano et al. [53] developed an income-based model to estimate electricity consumption, linking appliance ownership (modelled with a Gompertz curve) to consumption using a Gamma distribution calibrated via regression.

Poblete-Cazenave and Pacahuri [54] used micro-data from national surveys to estimate electricity demand in developing nations. They found that appliance adoption varies with nation, appliance type, environment, and income. In all four studied countries, entertainment accounted for a significant share of consumption, while rising incomes shifted demand toward food preparation and preservation, and clothing care.

Williams et al. [55] conducted a customer-focused analysis, segmenting 821 using a k-means clustering algorithm based on mean normalized load curves and daily electricity consumption. Exploratory graphical analysis sought to link these variables to customer categories, such as public premise, home, business, or mixed-use. Bahaj and James [56] compared load profiles and daily electricity demand across four rural microgrids with the same capacity. Consistent with Louw et al. [31], they found that consumption dynamics are cost-sensitive, driven by the relationship between income and tariff. In one system, prepayment adoption reduced overdue payments and dropouts, increasing consumption.

Hartvigsson et al. [57], analysed a Tanzanian microgrid at short- and long-term scales. Load profiles were evaluated for performance metrics

		Drivers							Appliance Ownership Data			
		Socio-Economic	Dwelling	Appliance	Past-demand	Supply	Alternative energy sources	Geographical	Cultural	Presence	Number	Usage Pattern
Entries	Source 1	Village 1	HH 1									
			HH 2									
			HH 3									
			...									
			HH n									
	Source 2	Village 2	...									
			...									
		Village 3	HH ...									
			...	HH ...								
			Village j	HH ...								
	HH ...								
			...									
			...									
			Village k	HH m								
			...									

Fig. 2. Structure of the proposed database. HH: Household.

Fig. 3. Flowchart of Database filling. Sources: Beck et al. [64]; World Bank [65]; JRC [66]; NASA [67]; GPW v4: Gridded Population of the World version 4 [68]; Meta - Data for Good [69]. QGIS logo under CC BY-SA 3.0 license.

Table 2
Share of available drivers and number of respondents for each source.

Source	Share of drivers	N° of respondents
CEFA	57 %	254
CLASP	23 %	2729
ESMAP	71 %	11875
FUNAE	24 %	210
LSMS+	64 %	1184

Fig. 4. Response rate duration curves.

like load factor, while 30 months of electricity expenditures, tied to tariffs, trained regression algorithms. Results revealed strong seasonality in consumption due to the agricultural-based economy. Business load profiles also varied significantly by type emphasizing the need to consider business activities and seasonality in system sizing.

Socio-economic drivers are the most commonly used across the reviewed literature, followed by drivers related to the techno-economic parameters of appliances and electricity supply technologies. Cultural drivers are the least considered, likely due to the challenges of data collection and classification, as well as the engineering focus that excludes such analysis [58].

In both *appliance ownership* and *load profile* literature, most driver classes are represented. However, within *appliance ownership* studies, this broad coverage is consistent across individual studies (except [29]), whereas *load profile* studies often focus on a narrower set of categories. Similarly, studies on *demand evolution* show near-complete coverage of driver categories.

Given the goal of this research – and the dependence of electricity demand, load profiles and demand evolution on appliance ownership and usage patterns – the following sections will address all the identified drivers as drivers as influencing appliance adoption and use, forming the basis for the proposed methodology.

3. Data preparation and structure

This section describes the data collection and cleaning procedure used to build the dataset for training the machine-learning model discussed in Section 4.

3.1. Data collection

The dataset was built through an initial data collection covering most factors reviewed in Section 2, followed by the harmonization and integration of diverse data sources. Fig. 2 depicts the final structure of the harmonized database, where columns represent the drivers and appliance ownership data, and rows correspond to entries from different data sources, villages, or households. This structure streamlined data integration, as additional sources simply added rows without altering the column structure.

Three actions were undertaken to populate the dataset: i) interviews with energy access sector stakeholders to obtain data on appliance adoption and household socio-economic characteristics, ii) collection of existing databases relative to recently electrified communities based on

Table 3

Resume table of appliance adoption data in each source. Red: the variable is not present in the source. Yellow: the variable is present only in some of the source's entries. Green: the variable is present in all source's entries.

Variable	ESMAP	CLASP	LSMS+	CEFA	FUNAE
Presence	Present	Present	Present	Present	Present
Number	Partially present	Not present	Present	Present	Present
Power	Not present	Not present	Not present	Partially present	Present
Frequency of use	Not present	Not present	Not present	Partially present	Not present
Total time of use	Partially present	Not present	Not present	Present	Not present
Time windows of use	Not present	Not present	Not present	Present	Not present
Minimum time of use after turning on	Not present	Not present	Not present	Present	Not present

Fig. 5. Flowchart for prediction model development.

Fig. 6. Appliance presence recurrency within the database (in red the eight appliances considered in the analysis, being the most recurrent). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 7. Database size against threshold in agreement with Eq. 1.

Table 4
Appliance presence distribution.

Appliance	Presence	Absence	Delta
Phone Charger	0.662	0.338	32 %
Light bulb	0.865	0.135	73 %
Iron	0.513	0.487	2 %
TV	0.714	0.286	43 %
Refrigerator/Freezer	0.437	0.563	13 %
Radio/Stereo	0.515	0.485	3 %
DVD Player	0.479	0.521	4 %
Fan	0.425	0.575	15 %

field interviews, and iii) extraction of information from geographically explicit datasets to enrich the database.

3.1.1. Interviews with energy access stakeholders

Energy sector stakeholders in SSA, including private and public entities, academia, NGOs and international organizations, were contacted to share data from their past electrification projects. The goal was to gather information on household appliance use and socio-economic conditions. These interaction also allowed for testing the completeness and significance of the driver’s list. In a few cases, key insights led to the inclusion of drivers not identified in the literature review.

Three institutions shared on-field survey data. The Collaborative Labelling and Appliance Standards Program (CLASP), shared information from seven surveys conducted among customers of efficiency-based

Table 5
Values of the confusion matrices of the unbalanced and balanced models.

Model	TP	FP	TN	FN	Accuracy
Phone Charger Unbalanced	0.89	0.66	0.34	0.11	0.7
Phone Charger Balanced	0.69	0.42	0.58	0.31	0.65
Lightbulb Unbalanced	1	1	0	0	0.87
Lightbulb Balanced	0.65	0.41	0.59	0.35	0.64
Iron Unbalanced	0.75	0.29	0.71	0.25	0.73
Iron Balanced	0.74	0.27	0.73	0.26	0.74
TV Unbalanced	0.94	0.69	0.31	0.058	0.76
TV Balanced	0.71	0.32	0.68	0.29	0.7
Refrigerator/Freezer Unbalanced	0.74	0.17	0.83	0.26	0.79
Refrigerator/Freezer Balanced	0.79	0.21	0.79	0.21	0.79
Radio/Stereo Unbalanced	0.66	0.4	0.6	0.34	0.63
Radio/Stereo Balanced	0.64	0.37	0.63	0.36	0.64
DVD Unbalanced	0.62	0.34	0.66	0.38	0.64
DVD Balanced	0.67	0.39	0.61	0.33	0.64
Fan Unbalanced	0.73	0.22	0.78	0.27	0.76
Fan Balanced	0.82	0.3	0.7	0.18	0.75

appliances. The Comitato Europeo per la Formazione Agraria (CEFA) contributed data from five surveys in Tanzanian communities electrified by microgrids, as well as grid-connected and not electrified communities. Fundo de Energia (FUNAE), shared information from three surveys conducted in communities electrified by their microgrids in Mozambique.

3.1.2. Collection of existing databases

To further enhance the database, data from the World Bank’s open-data portal were integrated. Five datasets were selected and grouped into two categories. The first includes ESMAP campaigns for the Energy Access Diagnostic Reports based on the Multi-Tier Framework [59], with surveys from thirteen countries conducted between 2017 and 2019. Data from Kenya [60], Nigeria [61] and Zambia [62] were added to the database. The second category includes the Living Standards Measurement Study – Plus (LSMS+), which collects data on respondents’ economic opportunities and welfare. From this programme the Tanzanian survey was included [63].

3.1.3. Extraction of data from GIS databases

To further enrich the databases georeferenced factors were collected for each entry from the referenced sources. These factors include climate zone, derived from a Köppen-Geiger classification [64]; distance from the nearest national grid, based on World Bank data of built and planned African distribution lines [65]; distance from the nearest city, sourced from the Joint Research Centre’s (JRC) dataset of urban centres defined by population and built-up area thresholds [66]. Elevation data, measured in meters above sea level, obtained from the NASA’s Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) [67]. Population density estimates are sourced from the Gridded Population of the World (GPW) dataset, aligned with national censuses [68]. The relative wealth index, developed by Data For Good, estimates living standards using connectivity data, satellite imagery, and additional sources [69].

To ensure consistency across countries, geospatial variables are harmonized using the Database of Global Administrative Areas (GADM), which provides a unified categorization of administrative divisions.

The proposed data collection process harmonizes different datasets, enriching them with cross-referenced information suitable for machine-learning models. This approach is a novel contribution to appliance adoption studies and can be easily adopted and improved due to its open-source nature [10].

3.2. Database structure

Fig. 3 outlines the database construction process and provides an overview of its size and scope.

The database includes sixty drivers of appliance adoption - potential factors influencing ownership – and seven appliance variables to be estimated by models trained on the drivers.

Table 2 summarizes the total number of respondents and the percentage of input variables present per each source. ESMAP is the richest source, both in terms of completeness and respondents count. While CEFA and LSMS + have a high share of input variables, CEFA has fewer respondents. CLASP and FUNAE, have fewer input variables, making them less suitable for regression analysis due to the potential loss of predictive variables.

Geographically, Kenya has the highest representation in the dataset with 6534 entries, followed by Nigeria (3669), Zambia (3622) and Tanzania (1680). Fewer instances are available for Uganda, Mozambique, Rwanda, and Senegal. This distribution reflects the geographic scope of the sources, as the three most represented countries are covered by ESMAP.

Table 2 summarizes data availability across drivers by source, but it does not capture the completeness of individual variables. A variable inclusion in each source does not indicate how many non-empty entries it contains, as response rates vary within sources. Fig. 4 illustrates this

Fig. 8. Accuracy comparison between Logistic regression and Dummy classifier in "ESMAP original".

Fig. 9. Accuracy trends during Recursive Feature Reduction.

Table 6
Comparison between the four final configurations.

Configuration	N° input variables	N° respondents
A oversampled	23	3106
A enlarged	32	2165
B oversampled	13	3738
B enlarged	25	2012

issue using source-specific response rate duration curves, which plot the number of variables (x-axis) with response rates equal to or exceeding the value on the y-axis.

Fig. 4 indicates that ESMAP, LSMS+, and CEFA are the most suitable for statistical analysis due to their higher response rates compared to the other two sources.

Analysing respondent categories reveals that 100 % of entries in

ESMAP and LSMS + are households (as opposed to businesses or public services). Thus, using these sources for model training focuses the analysis to households. However, the methodology could be extended to non-households if sufficient data quality is ensured.

Each database source is distinct in the appliances it investigates and the variables it collects. While appliance presence is the only adoption data common to all sources, other variables are more specific to individual datasets. Table 3 resumes this heterogeneity.

Table 3 reveals partial coverage of output variables across most sources, with CLASP offering the least information, collecting only appliance presence. In contrast, CEFA is the most comprehensive, with all variables at least partially covered.

For developing the machine learning models, three data subsets are used: "ESMAP", from now referred to as "ESMAP original", "LSMS+", and "CEFA".

Fig. 10. Accuracy comparison between the four configurations.

Fig. 11. Results of external validation on LSMS+ (above) and CEFA (below).

4. Methodology of the prediction models

This section outlines the methodology for building the appliance ownership prediction model. Fig. 5 presents a flowchart detailing the steps in this phase of the work.

After selecting the machine-learning model, data pre-processing normalizes the raw data and prepares the subset for model calibration. A portion of the data, the validation set, is reserved for final validation and excluded from training. Following pre-processing, a preliminary model is built and optimized to maximize performance. Validation is

Fig. 12. Features importance across the models, along with average values. For climate zones, “lev 1” stands for “at GADM level 1”. 1.0 is tropical, rainforest; 3.0 is tropical, savannah; 6.0 is arid, steppe, hot; 9.0 is temperate, dry summer, warm summer; 11.0 is temperate, dry winter, hot summer; 15.0 is temperate, no dry season, warm summer. In line with the Koppen-Geiger classification [64].

then conducted using data not included in training. The following subsections detail each step of the process.

4.1. Model selection

The choice of the machine-learning model depends on the nature of the target variable [70]. The first step is selecting which of the output variables of the analysis. “Appliance presence” is chosen for its ubiquity across all sources and its simplicity. The analysis focuses on the eight most commonly owned appliances in the database. As Fig. 6 shows, these appliances are owned by over 2000 respondents, deemed an acceptable size.

Predicting a Boolean variable, such as the presence of an appliance, constitutes a classification problem. Since inputs and outputs are predefined, supervised machine learning algorithms are appropriate [71]. In this study, high interpretability is prioritized to provide actionable insights for future electrification efforts. Neural networks and random forests are excluded due to their lower interpretability. Given the unknown qualitative input-output relationships and the likelihood of collinearity effects from the diverse input variables, the algorithm must handle these challenges and test irrelevant feature robustly.

Logistic regression is selected as it balances these requirements effectively [72].

Applying a logistic regression model invokes two implicit constraints. First, the dependent variable must be binary, which applies to Boolean variables representing appliance ownership. Second, a sufficiently large dataset size is required. Determining the exact size has been extensively studied in the literature. For this work, the criterion in

Equation (1) is adopted, as recommended by previous studies [73,74].

$$n = C_1 + C_2 \cdot i \tag{1}$$

Where, n is the dataset size, and i the number of explanatory variables in the model. The coefficients C_1 and C_2 , derived from the literature [75], are set to 500 and 50 respectively. This constraint is then applied to determine the proportion of the dataset to analyse, as shown in Fig. 7.

In conclusion this research focuses on eight appliance adoption datasets, each representing one appliance. Accordingly, eight separate logistic models are developed.

4.2. Preliminary models construction

To ensure robustness and reliability, each of the eight models is tailored to specific appliances and evaluated using repeated stratified 10-fold cross-validation (CV), a widely adopted method [76,77]. Logistic Regression performance depends on the hyperparameter C , the inverse of regularization strength; higher C values mean lower penalization and vice versa. CV is used for hyperparameter tuning, testing 200 values between 10^{-5} and 10^5 selecting the one that maximises performance.

Model performance is evaluated using three metrics: model accuracy, precision and recall, defined as in Ref. [77] and shown in Equations (2)–(4).

$$accuracy = \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{FP + FN}{TP + TN}\right)} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (2)$$

$$precision = \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{FP}{TP}\right)} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (3)$$

$$recall = \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{FN}{TP}\right)} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (4)$$

Where TP is True Positive, FP is False Positive, TN is True Negative and FN is False Negative.

When a dataset has highly imbalanced classes, accuracy often produces biased results favouring the dominant class, losing validity. To address the Accuracy Paradox [78], a weighted loss function with penalties inversely proportional to class frequency can be applied. While this typically reduces accuracy, it yields a more representative evaluation of model performance.

To further validate results, precision and recall should align closely with accuracy [77]. The performance of the models trained on “ESMAP original” is hence assessed using such metrics. Accuracy results are benchmarked against a dummy classifier that predicts the most frequent class. For appliance ownership prediction, comparing logistic regression with a dummy classifier demonstrates the benefit of a predictive model over simply assuming the presence or absence of appliances based on class frequency.

4.3. Calibration

A preliminary model calibration is performed to identify the most relevant input variables for each appliance type. To address data availability constraints, the ESMAP dataset is used due to its large size in both variables and entries. A feature importance test is performed on the “ESMAP original” dataset.

In parametric linear models like logistic regression, variable importance is indicated by the estimated coefficients, with higher absolute values denoting greater relevance [52]. Here i denotes the i -th variable and k the tested machine-learning model.

$$importance_{e_{i,k}} = |coeff_{i,k}| \quad (5)$$

The results are rescaled between 0 and 1 for inter-model comparisons. The average values across models are then computed with Equation (6), where n is the number of models predicting appliance presence.

$$importance_{e_i} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n importance_{e_{i,k}} \quad (6)$$

Once $importance_{e_i}$ is determined, variables are progressively discarded, from least to most relevant, to evaluate the drop in average model accuracy as features are reduced - a process known as Recursive Feature Elimination. The goal is to determine if similar accuracy can be obtained with fewer variables, simplifying and reducing the cost of surveys.

This process identifies the key factors needed to estimate appliance adoption, a novel contribution of this study.

4.4. External validation

After selecting and validating the optimal configuration on the ESMAP dataset using repeated stratified 10-fold CV, external validation is performed on the LSMS+ and CEFA subsets. Since these subsets lack some variables from the optimal configuration, the input pool is reduced to match their structure, resulting in some accuracy loss compared to the complete ESMAP dataset.

To address the limited entries in the CEFA dataset, missing values are

imputed using the Mean Imputation technique [79], replacing them with the variable’s mean. Appliance ownership models are validated on both sources by comparing three scenarios: the original ESMAP configuration, a “tailored” ESMAP configuration adapted to CEFA or LSMS + input pools, and performance on the external source. This approach evaluates the accuracy loss due to the input pool reduction versus validation on a different source.

5. Results

5.1. Preliminary models construction

The distribution of appliances presence in the “ESMAP original” dataset varies significantly by appliance, as shown in Table 4. Phone chargers, light bulbs and TVs are predominantly present, with differences between presence and absence of 32 %, 73 % and 43 % respectively. Irons, radios/stereos and DVD players show nearly balanced distribution, with differences under 5 %. Refrigerators/freezers and fans slightly favour absence, with differences of 13 % and 15 %, respectively.

As described in Section 4.2, the unbalance in appliance distributions requires applying a loss function with a penalty term for the logistic regression models to address the Accuracy Paradox. Table 5 presents confusion matrices ab accuracy values for unbalanced and balanced models. In unbalanced models, higher imbalance leads to higher accuracy at the expense of poor prediction for the minority class. For instance, in the highly unbalanced case of light bulbs, the model predicts “presence” in all instances, achieving 100 % accuracy for owners, but 0 % for non-owners, resulting in an overall accuracy of 87 % due to the predominance of “presence”.

Balanced models improve minority class predictions but reduce overall accuracy, as seen in the light bulb case, where accuracy drops by 23 %. These effects are less pronounced for appliances with balanced distribution, like radio/stereo.

After model fitting, repeated stratified 10-fold CV is performed for internal validation. To address data imbalance, accuracy, precision, and recall metrics are evaluated and compared with a “most-frequent” dummy classifier. Fig. 8 shows that logistic regression consistently outperforms the dummy classifier for balanced or slightly unbalanced appliances. For refrigerator/freezer, the best performing model, accuracy reaches 78.76 %, offering 22.49 % improvement over the dummy classifier’s assumption of absence.

For highly unbalanced appliances, results are less straightforward. TV and phone charger models show slight accuracy deficits of 0.95 % and 1.15 %, respectively, compared to the dummy classifier, which benefits from the unbalanced distributions. The issue is more pronounced for light bulbs, where the dummy classifier achieves 86.60 % accuracy, leading to a negative delta of 22.58 %. Predicting universal light bulb presence is more precise than applying a model, prompting its exclusion from further analyses. Conversely, phone charger and TV are retained, as subsequent steps may improve their performance.

On average, the preliminary models improve prediction performance by roughly 8 % over the Dummy Classifier: increasing to 12 % when the light bulb model is excluded.

5.2. Calibration results

The calibration process begins by identifying the least relevant variables among the 46 in the “ESMAP original” dataset. Features are ranked by average importance across models and removed one at a time through recursive feature reduction. This estimates the maximum achievable accuracy while progressively reducing input variables.

Fig. 9 shows a general decreasing trend, starting with a slow decline followed by a sharp accuracy drop when only the most critical features remain. Phone charger and TV models show some fluctuations, likely due to the discarding process based solely on average feature importance, causing premature removal of variables important for specific

appliances and oscillating behaviour.

The initial plateau indicates that several variables have minimal impact and could be excluded, reducing survey length. As described in the Methodology, this approach also increases the number of eligible respondents after NaN discarding. Two configurations, A and B, are selected, corresponding to 1 % and 2 % accuracy reduction compared to “ESMAP original”. Configuration A includes 23 variables, while B contains 13.

The surplus of respondents from the dataset size constraint can either expand the training sample (creating oversampled versions of A and B) or allow the inclusion of previously discarded variables. Each discarded variable is individually added to A and B to assess the marginal accuracy gain, forming configurations “A enlarged” and “B enlarged”.

Table 6 summarizes the four configurations, listing their input variables and respondents counts.

Fig. 10 compares the performance of the four configurations to determine the optimal model. “B enlarged” achieves the highest average accuracy, outperforming all models except for iron, where it matches “A enlarged”, and fan, where “A oversampled” performs 3.0 % better.

“B enlarged” is selected as the optimal configuration with 71.7 % accuracy and used for external validation. It outperforms “ESMAP original” by 2.39 % while reducing the number of features from 46 to 25.

5.3. External validation results

Since LSMS+ and CEFA, the two datasets employed for external validation, lack some of the input variables from “B enlarged”, two reduced configurations are created: “B enlarged downsized” with 17 variables for LSMS+ and 18 for CEFA, compared to the original 25.

The first plot in Fig. 11 shows the performance of “B enlarged downsized for LSMS+” tested on LSMS+ data, alongside results from the dummy classifier, “B enlarged”, and the internally validated “B enlarged downsized for LSMS+” on ESMAP. The 1.74 % average accuracy reduction between the two “B enlarged” models reflects a moderate loss due to removing eight low-importance variables.

External validation shows a 10 % accuracy drop compared to internal validation, though the model still outperforms the dummy classifier. Results vary by appliance: the refrigerator/freezer model achieves 81 % accuracy, outperforming the dummy classifier by 26.35 %. TV and DVD player models show smaller gains of 3.24 % and 9.13 %, respectively. Conversely, radio/stereo and fan models perform worse than the dummy classifier, with -9.55% and -13.13% accuracy deltas. Phone chargers and irons models could not be validated due to missing LSMS+ data.

Similar results are observed for CEFA, as shown in the second plot of Fig. 11. Despite “B enlarged downsized for CEFA” containing one more feature than its LSMS+ counterpart, its accuracy drop from “B enlarged” is more than twice as large (4.15 %) due to the exclusion of critical variables like dwelling quality and years in the community.

External validation results are worse than LSMS+, with overall accuracy slightly below the dummy classifier. Appliance-specific results vary widely: refrigerator/freezer and iron models achieve $+45.11\%$ and $+25.66\%$ gains, respectively, while TV, phone charger and radio/stereo show declines of -41.29% , -21.46% and -9.47% . Due to missing data in CEFA’s questionnaires, DVD player and fan models could not be validated.

6. Discussion

The open-access nature of this work contrasts with the general reluctance toward data sharing encountered during the data collection stage. While concerns about competitive advantages are understandable for private entities, the authors believe that all stakeholders can benefit from collective research enabled by data sharing [10].

Additionally, many interviewed players lacked data-driven sizing methodologies, relying instead on simplistic assumptions-based approaches. Expanding the database could help these entities adopt more

accurate sizing models supported by simple yet reliable surveys. Notably, the “B enlarged” dataset, which achieved the highest prediction accuracy, includes only 25 features, estimated to require just 14 survey questions due to their specific nature.

This insight supports reducing pre-electrification surveys length, addressing the common issue of questionnaire fatigue, which lowers data quality [80]. Fig. 12 shows feature importance for each model as well as the average, for the features with importance above median value, expressed as rescaled absolute coefficient values between 0 and 1.

Comparing models for different appliances reveals common features influencing ownership. Household wealth proxies such as “monthly expenditure”, “dwelling quality index”, and “motorized vehicle ownership” positively impact appliance presence, aligning with findings from Rao and Ummel, Dominguez et al., and Richmond et al. [26,28,40]. “Measurement age” indicates that appliance ownership increases over time after electrification, consistently with Richmond et al., Williams et al., Lorenzoni et al., and Fobi et al. [28,42–44]. Higher “education of household head” also correlates with greater appliance ownership, possibly reflecting better electricity awareness or higher income, as suggested by Rao and Ummel [26], though contrary to Kurata et al. [27]. Additionally, more hours of electricity availability encourage appliance purchases, supporting conclusions from Dominguez et al. [33].

Two variables consistently show a negative effect on appliance ownership. The first is “years spent in the community by household head”, which may act as a proxy for the age of the household head, suggesting that older heads may be less prone to electricity and appliance adoption. Alternatively, longer community residence may indicate a conservative attitude, leading to hesitance in adopting new appliances. The second is “weekly frequency in tariff payment”, implying that frequent payments are perceived as more burdensome than less frequent ones. This finding contrasts with Williams et al. [42], which reported a preference for small, frequent payments.

The “climate zone” variable positively influences fan ownership, in “tropical savannah” or “hot arid” zones, where cooling is essential, while its effect is negative in temperate climates. Other features show mixed effects across appliances requiring further research to understand their impact.

Prediction models are most useful for appliances with moderate population penetration where distribution is not strongly unbalanced. For appliances with extremely high or low penetration, assuming their presence or absence may be simpler and more reliable.

External validation revealed performance drop for CEFA, whose collection process differed significantly from ESMAP’s. While ESMAP and LSMS+ followed standardized methodologies, CEFA’s data were more heterogeneous and inconsistent both within and across questionnaires. This highlights the critical need for harmonized data collection processes to improve the reliability and scalability of appliance ownership prediction models.

6.1. Limitations and future work

Future work could focus on expanding the database, integrating additional ESMAP and LSMS+ questionnaires and extending the tool’s geographical scope beyond SSA. On the prediction side, models could estimate other appliance-related variables, such as quantity and power rating.

This study conducted a static analysis of time’s effect on appliance ownership using the “measurement age” variable. Since LSMS+ surveys are longitudinal, collected periodically and addressing the same respondents, future integration of past survey rounds could better capture the time dynamics, as only the latest data were used in this work.

7. Conclusions

This study introduced a novel methodology for estimating appliance adoption using a data-driven machine-learning model supported by a

comprehensive literature review. The review guided extensive data collection and harmonization processes involving socio-economic, weather and appliance data. The literature analysis proved essential in identifying relevant features and databases. Despite challenges in harmonization, the proposed procedure effectively addressed them. The logistic-regression based model achieved promising accuracy, sometimes exceeding 70 %, confirming the study's validity. A recursive feature reduction test identified the smallest critical subset of survey questions for predicting appliance adoption.

The resulting harmonized database includes 16252 respondents and 99 variables. Of these, 77 features are studied as potential drivers of appliance ownership and usage, while nine serve as model outputs, to be used in stochastic load profile generators. The database integrates five survey-based sources and geospatial data. Significant differences were found across sources, regarding data collection methods and available variables. While harmonization resolved format inconsistencies, missing variables remains a challenge.

Seven prediction models for appliance ownership were developed, refined, and tested through internal and external validation, achieving an average internal validation accuracy of 71.66 % using only 17 input variables. Wealth-related variables strongly influenced appliance ownership, while time dynamics played a key role, as longer electrification periods positively impacted all appliances. Supply-side factors, including electricity reliability and low-frequency payment systems, also promoted appliance adoption. Climate zones influenced the purchase of cooling appliances like fans. These findings provide a basis for designing shorter, reliable surveys.

This work establishes a framework for harmonizing data-sharing procedures to support rural electrification. The developed algorithm aids electricity planning and off-grid systems sizing. Insights into key drivers enhance the understanding of rural households' electricity use while guiding the creation of more efficient surveys critical for electrification efforts.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Nicolò Stevanato: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – original draft. **Davide Fioriti:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – original draft. **Tommaso Ferrucci:** Software, Methodology, Writing – original draft. **Luca Belloni:** Software, Methodology, Writing – original draft. **Lorenzo Rinaldi:** Software, Writing – review & editing. **Davide Poli:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Emanuela Colombo:** Supervision, Project administration, Writing – review & editing.

Data availability

The source code for the performed analysis and the collected data are available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7185210>.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used Chat-GPT 4.0 in order to improve language and readability. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data made available in open access.

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